

ON THE ISSUE OF THE FREQUENCY OF SPINAL CORD TUMORS

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Abstract: The incidence of spinal cord tumors increases to 3-4% due to improved diagnostics and increased patient referrals to neurosurgical hospitals. The ratio of spinal cord and brain tumors is 1:9. Spinal cord tumors most often occur at the age of 30-40 years.

Keywords: Key words: spinal cord, tumor, MRI, tracts.

Purpose of the work: to analyze the incidence of spinal cord tumors in hospitalized patients of the Neurosurgery Department of the Multidisciplinary Clinic of Samara State Medical University.

Materials and methods of research: This work is devoted to the study of the incidence rate of spinal cord tumors in 121 patients with spinal cord and spine tumors who were inpatients at the Neurosurgery Clinic of Samarkand State Medical University in the period from 2020 to 2023. All patients underwent routine general clinical and neurological examination, including tests on the Frankel and McCormick scales. MRI and MRI with contrast were used for radiation diagnostics. According to indications, MR tractography of the spinal cord and MSCT of the spine and spinal cord were performed. The results of the study among male patients were 60, female-61, children under 18 years of age-9. The age group of patients was divided according to the WHO classification (2021): under 18 years old - 9 (7.44%); 18-44 years old - young age - 55 (45.5%); 45-59 years old - middle age - 35 (29%); 60-74 years – elderly age - 22 (18.2%). The ratio of men and women was 1:1. Patients were divided into 4 groups based on clinical, neurological and radiological data: Group I – 82 (67.8%) with intradural extramedullary tumor localization, Group II – 12 (9.9%) with intramedullary localization, Group III – 27 (22.3%) with extradural paravertebral growth, recurrent tumors were observed in 6 patients (4.9%).

Fig.1. MRI of the cervical spinal cord.

Ultra-long intradural extramedullary tumor of the spinal cord at the level of VC5-VC6-VC7-VTh1-VTh2 with syringomyelia at the level of the cervical and thoracic sections of the spinal cord. Pronounced displacement, thinning, interruption of the course of the spinal cord tracts along the entire length.

In addition to the generally accepted classification, the distribution of patients was carried out according to our proposed classification (Mamadaliyev A.M.) of tumor growth along the length of the spinal cord and spine: nodular (or short) tumors at the level of one vertebra in 27 (22.3%) patients, tumors of medium length at the level of 2-3 vertebrae in 72 (59.5%) patients, long tumors at the level of 4-5 vertebrae in 20 (16.5%) patients and super-long tumors at the level of more than 5 vertebrae in 3 (2.5%) patients.

Conclusions: Thus, spinal cord tumors are a fairly common disease among patients of working age and require modern diagnostics to determine further treatment tactics.

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